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ECONOMIC DEREGULATION AND ECONOMIC GROWTH NIGERIA (1980-2025)

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Abstract: This paper was focused on the effect of economic deregulation on economic growth and development in Nigeria in the period 1980-2025 with real GDP and level of employment respectively as the relevant proxies for growth and development. The methodology for this study was econometrics. The study made use of secondary data such as total government expenditures, inflation rate, GDP and ratio of total government expenditures to GDP pooled from various sources such as Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Annual Reports and Accounts, National Bureau of Statistic (NBS), Economics texts, various journals of Economics etc. To test the hypotheses, the author made use of Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag models. The result of the analysis indicated that transition to market economy in Nigeria especially in the reviewed period was inflationary due to failure of fiscal policies resulting in poor growth and worsening unemployment. Again, public sector was excessively large in the reviewed period. Implications of the findings: inflationary pressure implied rising costs of investment and poor growth implied financial crisis and rising poverty. Excessively large public sector implies huge government expenditure, government deficits/debt financing and debt burden in Nigeria. Hence, the author recommended as follows: i. Nigeria requires a well-articulated planning program over time for growth and development. ii. Unless Nigeria devises means of managing resources efficiently, inflation would be difficult to control and growth development would remain a mirage. For instance surrounding proceeds from fuel subsidy withdrawal is the main source of inflation in Nigeria, among other recommendations.

Keywords: Deregulated Economy and Economic Growth

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The size of the public sector in the mixed economic system is measured by the percentage ratio of government purchases to GDP, or total government transfer payments to GDP. There are factors that influence the dynamics

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of these ratios such as efficiency in the use of resources, ability to control inflation, fiscal prudence, and effective fiscal control. All of these are aimed at improving productivity with limited resources. The public sector in the mixed economic system becomes excessive when the relationship between the denominator and numerators of these ratios turns negative often referred to as excessive use of bureaucratic apparatus in the allocation of economic resources (Collier, 2023). The shrinkage of the ratios implies reduced government purchases and transfer payments relative to improved productivity. This is what is referred to as economic deregulation or shrinkage of the public sector or transition to market economy. The idea of economic deregulation was earlier suggested by the World Bank and International Monetary Fund (IMF) at the wake of serious economic crisis of the 1980s Nigeria (Akinola, 2025). The whole essence of this policy was for the efficient management of the Nigerian, sustainable growth and development. The r Structural Adjustment Program (SAP) associated with program was to prepare a solid and effective ground for the market mechanism and to avoid the distortionary effect of defective structure.

Economic deregulation began in Nigeria in September 1986 when import and export licensing schemes meant for the allocation of foreign exchange were dismantled as part of external sector deregulation. Then all the marketing boards in Nigeria were scrapped. Instead, Second Tier Foreign Exchange markets (SFEM) were established (Ayodele, 1988). Then by 1987, the first and second windows of foreign exchange markets were merged to determine export and import equilibrium by the forces of demand and supply. On the goods and services market, domestic production and consumption were realigned to reflect the program of transition to market economy. In furtherance to this, public enterprises perceived to have performed below expectations were privatized. The reforms came with gradual withdrawal of government subsidies (Ayodele, 1994). By August 1987, assets and financial markets were deregulated. On the area of labor market, government tactically abolished the minimum wage law/salary structure which threatened unified grade level wage/salary structure earlier in operation in Nigeria. Prices in all sectors of Nigerian economy were liberalized. To foster economic liberalization, gradual removal of subsidies was enforced with its partial attempts in 2000s and full removal in May 2023 especially that of the oil sector by President Bola Tinubu. By the mid-1990s, public sector enterprises that performed below expectations were privatized on the basis that those enterprises were the major cause of public indebtedness and constituted a drain on the economy (Emerole, 2020). The focus of this paper is to relate economic deregulation with economic growth and development as well as to empirically verify the excessiveness of public sector in Nigeria. Economic deregulation implies removal of government controls on prices, industries and market to allow increased competition, and efficiency through the market mechanism. In the Nigerian context, due to improper checks, lack of political will to enforce efficiency companies gained market power which resulted in inflationary pressure. Liberalization of prices in the oil and gas sectors resulted in price increases. The removal of fuel subsidies led to sharp pump price hikes, rising transport costs, fuelling inflation, poor investment, dwindling growth and economic hardship. Rising inflation and liberalization of the external sector gave rise to serious devaluation of domestic currency and foreign exchange instability resulting in poor productivity in the industrial sector. Withdrawal of subsidies, inability to achieve efficiency and competition through privatization gave rise to monopoly power resulting in rising production costs, and rising production costs. Within the Keynesian context, the higher fuel pump prices acted as supply shocks which translated into high production costs for the energy dependent sectors such as the

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transport, manufacturing sectors etc. shifting the aggregate demand curve leftward causing cost push inflation, reduced output and GDP growth. Keynesian theory highlights the demand side effects of high prices of energy in which rising prices of energy result in rising prices of goods and services, rising inflation, erosion of consumer disposable income and confidence, reduced spending on nonessential goods, and dwindling economic growth. For the oil importing countries like Nigeria, a situation like this amplifies fiscal strain through higher import bills which may likely crowd out public investment in infrastructure and social services. From the stand point of endogenous growth model, sustained high prices hinder human capital accumulation and innovation by increasing living costs, exacerbating inequality and poverty. Nigeria's version of economic deregulation has continued to raise some relevant questions such as: how excessive is Nigeria's public sector?; what is the effect of economic deregulation on inflation in Nigeria?; what is the effect of inflation on real growth in Nigeria?; what is the effect of economic deregulation on economic development in Nigeria? Hence, the general objective of this study is to determine empirically, whether large public sector really exists in Nigeria; while specific objectives are, to determine the effect of inflation on the relative size of government in Nigeria; to determine the effect of productivity on the relative size of government in Nigeria. The direction and magnitude of the outcome of these inquiries would throw light on the reality of transition to market economy in Nigeria. This paper would be of great interest not just to the general reader but also to the students of Nigerian economy, researchers and policy makers who must have been searching for more effective policies to fast track Nigeria's development process in the face of poor performance of the country's economy to date. The rest of this paper is structured as follows: section two is conceptual issues; section three is theoretical framework and methodology; section four is presentation of results and analysis; section five is summary of results, conclusion and recommendations.

2.0 Conceptual Issues

Transition to market economy or economic deregulation or shrinkage of the public sector in the mixed economic system presupposes much reliance on the market forces for the allocation of economic resources/ minimal government presence. It implies reduction in the size of government budget relative to GDP. Transition to market economy implies the alteration of the mixed economy towards the market system as against the size of government in terms of excessively large government consumption expenditures relative to GDP (Barro & Lee, 1993).

According to the classical doctrine, excessively large size of government consumption expenditure relative to GDP usually has negative effect on growth. Large public sector in the mix implies induced distortions of the market. Excessive public sector implies stifle private initiatives, private investment and economic growth. In line with Adam Smith's inquiry into wealth of Nations, the major problem of every society is the capacity to increase the available scarce economic resources. Excessively large government expenditures, may give rise monetary growth, inflationary pressure, reduced investment and growth. Much consumption expenditures negate economic growth. GDP is the fundamental measure used to assess the overall health and performance of the economy. It represents the total values of goods and services produced within the country's borders over a specific period typically a year or quarter. It serves several critical functions. It helps to track economic growth over time. An increasing GDP indicates that the economy is expanding leading to more jobs, higher income levels, and improved standard of living. Conversely, a declining GDP signals recession, declining productivity

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etc. During periods of low GDP growth, government introduces stimulus measures such as increased public spending or reduced taxes to boost economic activities. GDP figures influence investors' confidence. Growing government deficits and public debts, give impetus to increases in taxes and heavy tax burden, which may depress private savings, investment, growth, resulting in large size of government. If the size of the ratio of government expenditure to GDP is excessively large it implies that the larger aspect of government expenditure does not contribute to growth which results monetary growth and inflationary pressure (Baumol, 1967). According to Keynes (1936), counter cyclical policies give rise to increased public sector in the mixed economic system and contradict market development. Hence the following mathematical model:

$$\frac{GE}{GDP} = F(\text{Infl}, \text{GDP}) \dots\dots\dots 2.1)$$

Where $\frac{GE}{GDP}$ = public sector size of mixed economic system; Infl= inflation, GDP gross domestic product. The

$$\text{econometric model is as follows: } \frac{GE}{GDP} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{INFL} + \beta_2 \text{GDP} + \varepsilon_0$$

Infl>0, Implies that inflationary pressure expands the public sector size in the mixed economic system.
GDP<0, implies that the public sector in the mixed economic system is excessively large.

2.1 REVIEW OF RELEVANT THEORIES

Theories why the size of government increases abound. Baumol's Disease (1967), Bowen and Downs (1943, 1957) Income Distributional Theory, castle(1982) Socialist Government Control Theory, Keynes (1936) Counter cyclical Theory, Pommerehne & Schneider(1978) Fiscal illusion theory, have long pointed out the factors that contribute to the increasing size of government and hinder the development of the market. Baumol(1967) in his disease theory, argued that the cost of producing government tends to rise secularly; and the inherent nature of public goods create problem for their pricing ,resulting in difficulty in improving the productivity and output growth in public goods. Bowen& Downs (1943, 1957) income distributional theory argued that the need for income distribution is a factor why the size of government continues to increase especially in the developing countries. The income distribution theory originated from median voter theory in which competition and redistribution of income appear to be the two major factors that influence positively the size of government. In line with this construct, When the franchise is extended to include more voters below the median income ,the pressure for income distribution on politicians will cause them budget for income increase which tends to increase the size of government. And when there is a clear difference between political and market processes, government tends to grow rapidly. Castle (1982) socialist government control theory, observed that government of socialist persuasions tends to increase public spending at a faster rate than the bourgeois government which results in large size of government. And the attitude towards public spending of different parties depends on the type of party and the type of spending. For instance party A may favour increased spending on defense and education; while party B may favour increased spending on social welfare character. Hence there is a positive and close relationship between public sector growth and the color of the party in power. In line with Keynes(1936) counter cyclical theory, government size expands when government reacts to recession by taking recourse to expansionary fiscal policy which may result in increasing size of government .Again, the information costs associated with the assessment of public revenue especially when

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taxes imposed in the course of market transaction appear to be less visible. Similarly, revenue assessment of public goods is complex when government takes recourse to debt refinancing. This is because consumers of public goods will encounter the difficulty of discounting and capitalizing future tax burden from current public debt incurred. This is why the complex revenue system as observed with the public sector poses much difficulty in the assessment of total fiscal burden. This is referred to as fiscal illusion that keeps the size of government expanding (Pommerehne & Schneider 1978). In line with Wagner (1890) demand side theory of public sector expansion, government adjusts its size in direct response to the demands of the citizenry, unless such government is operating independently of the wants and desires of the governed (excessive government) as opposed to a responsive government. Wagner identified three reasons why the size of government keeps expanding. The size of government keeps expanding due to industrialization, increased contractual and legal relationships, and increased demands for more public regulative and protective activities, urbanization and population explosion. Baumol (1967), Bowen & Downs (1943, 1957), Castle (1982) and Wagner (1890) theories of public sector expansion capture the structural parameters of the Nigerian economy. These theories explain perfectly well why the public sector has expanded over the years in Nigeria. Keynes (1936) counter cyclical theory explained further why inability to control expenditures and budget deficits contributed to expanding government size in Nigeria; while Pommerehne & Schneider (1978) fiscal illusion theory provide explanation why the public utility users in Nigeria cannot fully discount and capitalize future tax burden from current public debt which results in growing size of government. Note rising public debt service payments, implies growing size of government as well as rising relative of government, and dwindling growth. Huge expenditures of government without output growth have always resulted in monetary growth and inflation. In the name of deregulation, the issues of public debts, high rates of inflation and unemployment, capacity underutilization, rising external dependence and poverty have continued to worsen.

3.0 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical basis for this study has been couched under the aggregate demand management approach distinct from Keynesian approach but more of the monetarists approach. However, Nigeria's approach, emphasized free market oriented paradigm viewed from floating exchange rate, interest rate, deregulation of overall sectors, privatization of public enterprises, liberalization of prices, control of expenditures and budget deficits, all are aimed towards the monetarist approach. Therefore, the monetarists approach captures appropriately the structural parameters of the Nigerian economy. And the quantity theory of money becomes very relevant considering the rising inflation in Nigeria. Therefore, if the velocity of money (k), is reasonably stable especially at the long run, a change in the quantity of money (m) will cause the nominal product (Q) which is the same price of the product (p) and real output (RQ) to change by approximately the same proportion with the quantity of money (m). At equilibrium, the quantity of money becomes: $M = K P y$

Theoretically k and y are assumed to be constant. Then it is output (y) at the short run that explains why a change in the quantity of money (m) through credit expansion directly goes to price (p) to allow for equilibrium, which implies that as m expands, k remains stable. Hence what is to be controlled mainly is p to avoid rising inflation. But the remedy for the rising p is y which is the level of productivity. This is why Nigeria's chronic capacity underutilization and high rate of unemployment are worrisome. And the solution for

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inflation and deflation is to manage productivity with monetary expansion. This implies that monetary expansion must be channeled to stimulate wealth and asset creation as well as output growth .Inflationary package should be executed within the framework of growth, capacity utilization, mitigation of unemployment, stable prices and improved quality of life. According to the neoclassical view, large government expenditures without significant growth in output results in growth or GDP. A situation like this gives rise to monetary growth, rise in prices and inflation.

GDP Note: excessive growth in government expenditures relative to GDP is a relevant proxy for public sector growth.

Therefore the objectives of this paper are to determine empirically whether there is excessive public sector by examining the relationship between the relative size of government and GDP and to determine the effect of inflation on growth in Nigeria.

$$GDP = F\left(\frac{GE}{GDP}, INFL\right) \dots \dots \dots (3.1)$$

$$GDP = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \frac{GE}{GDP} + \alpha_2 INFL \dots \dots \dots (3.2)$$

$$GDP < 0; \frac{GE}{GDP} < 0; INFL < 0$$

3.2 Methodology

Methodology for this paper is purely econometrics involving statement of theory, specification of model, obtaining of data, estimation of empirical model, hypothesis testing and forecasting. The author employed annual secondary data such as government expenditure, Gross Domestic Product ,Inflation rate, ratio of government expenditure to GDP, as a proxy for the size of public sector, pooled from National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), CBN Annual Reports and Accounts, World Bank and various sources. To estimate equation 3.2 Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) method was employed. To estimate the econometrics models 3.1 and 3.2, the researcher made use of Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique.

Decision Rule

GE/GDP < 0 Implies excessive public sector

Inflation < 0 Implies depressing effect on GDP

GDP < 0 Implies depressed investment and growing size of government

4.0 Presentation and Analysis of Results

4.1 Presentation of Results

Table 4.1: ARDL Test Result

Dependent variable: REAL GDP

Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	t-stat	Probability
GDP(-1)	0.809268	0.078745	10.27710	0.0000
$\frac{GE}{GDP}$	-1.880000	1.040000	-1.801976	0.0076
Infl	-0.668287	0.137248	4.869203	0.0000
C	1056291	651241.3	1.621966	0.1111

Source: Author’s computation

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R-Squared	0.847150	Mean dependent var	6402229
Adjusted R-Squared	0.837979	S.D dependent var	1.446408
SE of Regression	57945112	Akaike Info Criterion	38.66908
Sum Square Resid	1.6800000	Schwarz Criterion	38.8060
Log Likelihood	-103.9795	Hannan-Quinn Criterion	38.71590
F-Statistic	92.37262	Durbin- Watson Statistics	2.235480
Prob (F-Statistic)	0.000000000		

Nigeria's much emphasis on free market oriented paradigm for economic development since the 1980s has received much theoretical attention without sufficient empirical response or evidence. This study is meant to bridge this empirical gap. The ARDL results presented in table 4.1 indicated that growth in real GDP in the previous period especially in the first period (Q (-1)) had significant positive effect on GDP in the reviewed period at less than 5% level of significance. For every 1% increase in real GDP, real GDP in the previous period contributed 0.81%. Government purchases per real GDP or relative size of government had significant negative effect on real GDP in the period 1970-2023 at less than 5% level of significance. For every 1% increase in real GDP, relative size of government had depressing effect of 1.9% (-1.9). This implies excessive government in the mixed economic system. The constant though positive was not statistically significant at 5% level. Hence it empirically evident that in Nigeria reduced state activities does not reflect reduced relative size of government. It also suggests excessive monetary growth, inflation and lack of expenditure restraint on the part of government. Table 4.2 presents the influence of inflationary pressure in the previous periods, real GDP, and relative size of government on inflationary pressure in Nigeria in the period 1970-2023. The results of ARDL tests indicated that inflation rate in the first period (INFL(-1)) had significant positive effect on the inflationary growth in the period 1970-2023. For every 1% increase in inflation rate inflation in the first period contributed 0.7%. Inflation second period (INFL (-2)) had significant negative or depressing effect on inflationary growth in the period 1970-2023 in Nigeria. This implies weak fiscal policy effectiveness in the period. For every 1% rise in inflation, inflation in the second period (INFL (-2)) contributed 0.34%. real GDP had no significant effect on inflation in the period 1970-2023 in Nigeria. Relative size of government (ceq) had significant positive effect on inflationary pressure at less than 5% level of significance in Nigeria in the period 1970-2023. For every 1% rise in inflation in the period relative size of government contributed 71.3%, implying excessive size of government under va deregulated economy.

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Summary of Findings

The impacts of deregulation policies beginning from the early 1980s in Nigeria appeared to have far reaching negative implications on all the sectors of the economy. Whatever positive results deregulation had achieved in Nigeria, yet the following major socio-economic problems are yet to be redressed: rising public debts, poor growth, high rates of inflation and unemployment, capacity underutilization, over external dependence and growing poverty level over the years. For instance, between 2007 and 2008, Nigeria's external debts grew from \$8.531b to \$13.13b representing 54% increase. The stock of the country's external debt in 2016 was \$31b, implying that between 2007 and 2016, Nigeria's foreign borrowing rose by 244%; the external debt service

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payments rose from \$0.7b in 2008 to \$ 2.5b in 2016 representing 257% increase. Interest payment alone on debt rose from \$0.09b in 2008 to \$0.6b in 2016 representing 567% increase.

5.1 Conclusion

From empirical evidence, there was excessively large size of the public sector in Nigeria. Deregulation policies appear not to have contributed to economic growth and development in Nigeria probably due to noncompliance fiscal reforms. Lack of expenditure restraint reflects the inability to control government deficits and public debt that resulted in the largeness of the public sector. The relative size of government was the major cause of monetary growth and inflationary pressure in Nigeria. Inflation distorted investment, growth and negated economic development. Other major factors that gave rise to inflationary pressure in Nigeria were liberalization of the economy relative to poor productivity, rising costs of businesses caused by fuel price increase and fuel subsidy withdrawal and energy caused by defects from privatization of the power sector. In conclusion, Nigeria's structural defects reinforce the distortions of the market system, to contradict the development of the market.

Recommendations

In line with the empirical findings, the following recommendations are preferred:

- i. Rural economy that sustains the mass majority of Nigerian people must be the primary concern of government. For instance, the wealth of this country is created the peasants who have been marginalized by the present economic order. Peasant class must be placed in the position where they can fully utilize their labor power for the creation of utility without due harassment, hindrance and exploitation.
- ii. Economic recovery in Nigeria must entail freeing the economy from the constraints that have hindered it from growth and development.
- iii. Nigeria requires a well-articulated planning program over time for growth and development.
- iv. Unless Nigeria devises means of managing resources efficiently, inflation would be difficult to control and growth development would remain a mirage. For instance surrounding proceeds from fuel subsidy withdrawal is the main source of inflation in Nigeria. Therefore, in line with the empirical findings, the researcher proffers following recommendations :

The government on regular basis must publish detailed reports on subsidy funds and spending; without strong transparency, and anticorruption efforts, fuel subsidy withdrawal is tough to sustain.

- v. . There is need for digital payments to prevent leakages and fraud.
- vi. The government must engage civil society and media for independent monitoring.
- vii. Anti-corruption agencies must be empowered to investigate misuse of subsidy proceeds.
- viii. Government must set up clear accountability frameworks.

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